

Dynamic SNR Estimation and Worst-Channel Elimination in Cooperative Compressed Sensing

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Abstract—This paper investigates a selective user cooperation strategy for cooperative compressed spectrum sensing in cognitive radio networks. By estimating the signal-to-noise ratio of compressed measurements for multiple secondary users, the proposed approach dynamically selects high-SNR users to participate in cooperative detection. This selection reduces the impact of noise from low-SNR users, significantly enhancing the quality and accuracy of sparse signal recovery. The methodology is validated through both simulations and an SDR-based implementation, demonstrating notable improvements in recovery accuracy and spectrum sensing performance, particularly in challenging, noisy environments.

Index Terms—Cooperative Compressed Spectrum Sensing, Selective User Cooperation, Signal-to-Noise Ratio, Sparse Signal Recovery, SDR, Cognitive Radio Networks.

I. INTRODUCTION

In modern communication systems, accurately estimating the Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) is crucial to optimizing performance, particularly in environments characterized by interference. This paper addresses the estimation of SNR for compressed measurements in cooperative sensing frameworks, where multiple nodes collaborate to improve signal detection and estimation. Using compressed sensing (CS) techniques, our aim is to develop methods capable of identifying and eliminating the worst-performing channels, thereby improving overall system efficiency. CS has emerged as a powerful tool for acquiring and processing sparse or compressible signals with significantly fewer samples than traditional methods. In cooperative sensing scenarios, multiple nodes collaborate to enhance performance by sharing information and leveraging diversity. However, the presence of channels with low SNR can degrade the overall performance of the system.

The paper [1] presents a channel estimation technique for massive MIMO systems that minimizes pilot overhead by integrating compressive sampling matching with sparsity adaptive matching pursuit. Enhances normalized mean square error (NMSE) performance at high SNR while lowering computational complexity compared to traditional methods.

The study [2] presents a method for estimating the unknown noise variance in CS problems, where measurements are often contaminated by additive noise. Accurately estimating the noise variance is important because it helps to improve the design of signal reconstruction algorithms. The authors in [3] propose low-complexity blind estimators for noise power, signal power, SNR, and MSE in multi-antenna mmWave systems, utilizing the sample median and sparsity in the beamspace representation of channels for efficient estimation.

Similar projects have already been completed. In this work [4], we examined the effectiveness of the effect of fusion rules on cooperative networks for CSS. The AND rule has the lowest false alarm rate P_f and a relatively high detection probability P_d for small networks, while the vote rule has the highest P_d for acceptable P_f according to **IEEE 802.22** cognitive radio standard. In addition, a virtualization strategy was proposed to improve SNR and size sensitivity performance. Another study [5] explores the use of the RMP recovery algorithm in conjunction with the AND rule that exhibits the lowest P_f for support tracking. The current literary works performed better under the suggested structure.

Both works in [4], [5] improve the detection performance of dense networks and require precise synchronization between channels for coherent integration. We are mostly interested in small networks for faisability and manageability purposes. To reduce complexity and improve performance at the same time, we proceed to a quick SNR estimation to sort channels and eliminate the worst one from the cooperation process. The estimation does not need to be highly precise since the exact SNR value does not matter too much. Estimating the SNR from two measurement periods can be a useful approach to isolate noise and improve sparse recovery in CS.

This method requires neither channel synchronization nor a large number of secondary users, with noticeable improvements even in small network configurations.

II. COMPRESSIVE SENSING

Compressed Sensing is an advanced signal processing method designed to reconstruct sparse or compressible signals using only a limited set of linear measurements. The key concept behind CS is its ability to take advantage of the signal's natural sparsity or compressibility when represented in an appropriate basis.

A sparse signal, which contains only a small number of non-zero components in a given basis Ψ^{-1} [6], can be compressed using the following expression:

$$y_{M \times 1} = \Phi x + b = \Phi_{M \cdot N} \Psi_{N \cdot N}^{-1} s_{N \cdot 1} + b_{M \cdot 1} \quad (1)$$

In this context, y represents the measurement vector, Φ is the sampling matrix, x is the signal sampled at the Nyquist rate, Ψ is the sparsifying matrix, b accounts for the noise, and s denotes the sparse vector. The compression is achieved through the sensing matrix $A = \Phi\Psi^{-1}$.

The goal is to reduce the size of the signal, achieving a sub-Nyquist sampling rate where $M \ll N$. Each measurement in the compressed vector represents a weighted sum of the components of the original signal. In the absence of noise, equation (1) becomes underdetermined, making it impossible to recover x or s directly from y . However, by exploiting the sparsity of s , characterized by its support $\text{supp}(s) = k \ll N$, it becomes feasible to reconstruct the signal. The sparsest solution can be found by solving:

$$s^0 = \underset{s}{\text{argmin}} |s|_0 \quad \text{s.t.} \quad y = As \quad (2)$$

Although solving for $|s|_0$ is NP-hard, it can be approximated through convex relaxation by minimizing $|s|_1$ [7], which is computationally feasible. The number of required measurements depends on the signal sparsity, the Nyquist rate, and the properties of the sampling matrix. Some common examples of measurement requirements include:

$$\begin{cases} M_{\min} \simeq 1.32K \log(N/K + 4) + 3 & \mathcal{N} \text{ and } \mathcal{B} \\ M_{\min} \simeq 1.7K \log(N/K + 1) + 1 & \text{AIC} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

One of two requirements must be satisfied for optimal and robust signal recovery: low mutual coherence, which is the greatest correlation between the columns of the sensing matrix, or the Restricted Isometry Property (RIP) [6], [8]. Numerous sampling matrices, including Toeplitz matrices, circulant matrices, and random matrices, have been presented [9], [10]. Although random matrices are easy to construct, they require a lot of computing power and memory to store data. Toeplitz and circulant matrices, on the other hand, are structured matrices that require fewer measurements for signal sampling and are computationally efficient.

There are various types of sparse signal recovery techniques, including deep learning, convex relaxation, greedy algorithms, and Bayesian approaches [9]. Convex relaxation is based on linear programming, or one-norm minimization, which provides excellent precision at the expense of computational complexity. The Augmented Lagrange Method (ALM),

Gradient Descent, and Least Squares are popular methods [11]. Greedy algorithms, which iteratively choose the most advantageous components based on the measurements, provide a simpler alternative to these methods due to their considerable complexity.

Although it breaks down the signal iteratively, the fundamental Matching Pursuit (MP) method may not be very accurate. By making sure the chosen components are orthogonal to the residual, Orthogonal Matching Pursuit (OMP) enhances MP and increases accuracy while controlling overfitting [12]. OMP still needs to be carefully adjusted and is susceptible to noise.

For wideband spectrum sensing in Cognitive Radio Networks (CRNs), Fast Matching Pursuit (FMP) is used in [13]. It achieves effective signal reconstruction at just 25% of the Nyquist rate, greatly speeding up performance compared to similar algorithms.

III. COOPERATIVE SENSING

Through information exchange and the use of diversity, several nodes work together in cooperative sensing to enhance system performance as a whole. Improved coverage, precision, and dependability may result from this. There are two primary categories into which cooperative sensing falls:

- Data fusion: The nodes combine their individual measurements to obtain a more accurate estimate of the target signal.
- Distributed processing: The nodes collaborate to perform joint signal processing tasks, such as compressed sensing or detection.

The existence of channels with low SNR is one of the main obstacles in cooperative sensing. These channels have the potential to add noise and impair system performance as a whole. Consequently, identifying and reducing the impact of low-SNR channels is crucial.

By successfully addressing problems such as multipath fading, CSS increases spectrum sensing efficiency and detection accuracy. However, cognitive radios (CRs) need to continuously identify primary user (PU) activities and limit interference because spectrum availability is dynamic.

Cooperative spectrum sensing (CSS), in which users work together to improve detection reliability, has been the subject of research. To enhance fusion procedures and minimize shadowing effects, for example, Bouzegag et al. [14] presented improved square law combining (SLC) rules.

Furthermore, to enhance wideband spectrum sensing (WSS) at sub-Nyquist rates, the combination of collaboration and CS has been investigated. Single-node and multinode systems can benefit from two approaches that decrease complexity and increase noise resistance [15].

Secondary users (SUs) send autocorrelation data to a fusion center (FC) for decision-making in a centralized CSS approach published in [16]. The Matching Pursuit algorithm is used to reconstruct signals, which reduces the impact of noise but increases complexity by requiring a high sampling rate for the computation of the autocorrelation matrix.

IV. DIFFERENTIAL MEASUREMENT TECHNIQUE FOR NOISE-REDUCED SIGNAL RECOVERY

The two sets of compressed measurements, \mathbf{y}_1 and \mathbf{y}_2 , are assumed to correspond to the same signal \mathbf{x} but to have distinct noise realizations:

$$\begin{aligned}\mathbf{y}_1 &= \Phi \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{n}_1 \\ \mathbf{y}_2 &= \Phi \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{n}_2\end{aligned}$$

where \mathbf{n}_1 and \mathbf{n}_2 are noise vectors, \mathbf{x} is the same signal and Φ is the same measurement matrix. The result of subtracting the two measurements is the following:

$$\mathbf{y}_{\text{diff}} = \mathbf{y}_1 - \mathbf{y}_2 = (\mathbf{n}_1 - \mathbf{n}_2)$$

The noise difference $\mathbf{n}_1 - \mathbf{n}_2$ is all that remains after the signal $\Phi \mathbf{x}$ is ideally canceled out. This makes it possible to estimate the noise power.

A. Noise Power Estimation

The noise difference $\mathbf{n}_1 - \mathbf{n}_2$ is a new noise vector, and its power can be calculated as:

$$P_{\text{new noise}} = \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{n}_1 - \mathbf{n}_2\|^2$$

Since $\mathbf{y}_{\text{diff}} = \mathbf{n}_1 - \mathbf{n}_2$, the noise power can be approximated as:

$$P_{\text{new noise}} \approx \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{y}_{\text{diff}}\|^2$$

B. Signal Power Estimation

Next, we estimate the signal power using one of the original measurements (assuming that both have the same signal):

$$P_{\text{signal}} = \|\Phi \mathbf{x}\|^2 \approx \|\mathbf{y}_1\|^2 - \|\mathbf{n}_1\|^2$$

To estimate $\|\mathbf{n}_1\|^2$, we use the noise difference:

$$\|\mathbf{n}_1\|^2 \approx \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{y}_{\text{diff}}\|^2$$

Thus, the signal power is approximated as:

$$P_{\text{signal}} \approx \|\mathbf{y}_1\|^2 - \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{y}_{\text{diff}}\|^2$$

C. SNR Estimation

Finally, the SNR can be estimated as:

$$\text{SNR} = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{P_{\text{signal}}}{P_{\text{new noise}}} \right)$$

where P_{signal} and $P_{\text{new noise}}$ are the estimated signal and noise power, respectively.

D. Considerations

1) *Signal Stability*: This method assumes that the signal \mathbf{x} remains constant over the two measurement periods. If the signal changes, the subtraction will not perfectly cancel it, affecting the noise estimate.

2) *Independent Noise*: The method also assumes that the noise vectors \mathbf{n}_1 and \mathbf{n}_2 are independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.) with the same variance. Correlated noise can bias the SNR estimate.

E. Use of SNR in Sparse Recovery

- **Noise-aware algorithms**: Recovery performance can be enhanced by algorithms such as Lasso or Basis Pursuit Denoising, which use the noise level to better tune their parameters.
- **Adaptive thresholding**: SNR estimation aids in establishing suitable thresholds for detecting significant coefficients, enhancing recovery accuracy in techniques like Matching Pursuit.
- **Stopping criteria**: In order to prevent overfitting of the noise, iterative algorithms can utilize the noise level to decide when to stop.
- **Cooperation**: When making decisions, we can choose the optimal channels in cooperative networks.

V. RESULTS

A sparse, wideband signal was used to drive the simulation. When one SU is removed, the network is large enough to retain the cooperation hypothesis. The AND rule serves as a hard fusion rule, and a greedy algorithm is used for recovery. The average SNR of the appropriate number of channels L on the y axis is represented by the SNR axis (x axis) in the 3D curves of Figure 1. The SNR fluctuation is the only difference between the first and second lines. $\Delta \text{SNR} = 1\text{dB}$, and 10dB is the expected value.

The recovered support portion of the cooperative compressed sensing technique is shown in Figures 1.a and 1.d. When removing the worst channel, both figures perform better in terms of cooperative detection probability Q_d . Cooperation in the original network (L -sized) is shown by the colored map, while the reduced network ($L-1$) is represented by the red grid.

Figures 1.b and 1.e demonstrate the improvement in Q_d . It is clearly seen that there is no negative value, indicating that the strategy is always effective. In medium SNR (around 6dB) and smaller networks, greater improvements are discernible. The cooperative false alarm rate Q_f is shown in the final two figures, 1.c and 1.f, for both fluctuation scenarios according to SNR and L . Transformation degradation is comparable to the new Q_f of the smaller network because the AND rule initially shows a relatively low Q_f . The maximum value complies with the previously specified **IEEE 802.22** CR requirement since it is less than 5×10^{-3} .

VI. SDR VALIDATION

As shown in Figure 2, we realized a framework according to the methods described in [5] to validate the suggested strategy. Eight receivers (USRP B210), a centralized fusion center, and a single transmitter (HackRF One) make up the network included in this framework. The frequency, phase, and timing of the system are carefully adjusted to provide accurate cooperative detection and precise synchronization.

Fig. 1. Cooperative detection probability and false alarm rate: (a) Q_d of L Vs $L-1$ channels (Δ SNR=1dB). (b) Q_d improvement (Δ SNR=1dB). (c) Q_f deterioration (Δ SNR=1dB). (d) Q_d of L Vs $L-1$ channels (Δ SNR=10dB). (e) Q_d improvement (Δ SNR=10dB). (f) Q_f deterioration (Δ SNR=10dB).

- **Frequency Calibration:** We used frequency calibration to ensure alignment at the receiver end and prevent frequency offset across receiving channels. This calibration process makes sure that frequency shifts will not interfere with signal detection, which is important for cooperative spectrum sensing.
- **Phase Calibration:** To align every channel with a specified reference channel, a phase correction mechanism is incorporated into the phase calibration procedure. Phase differences between receivers can reduce detection accu-

racy, particularly in cooperative setups where combined signals are examined; therefore, this alignment is crucial for coherent detection.

- **Timing and Synchronization:** A two-tiered clocking mechanism is used to produce synchronization. First, to guarantee alignment at a lower level, each pair of channels shares synchronization via the motherboard clock. Second, by coordinating the timing for every channel in the network, the central PC clock keeps the four motherboards in sync. Since any time misalignment could result in decreased cooperative detection efficiency, this multilayered synchronization strategy is crucial for efficient data fusion at the fusion center.

We used cooperative compressed sensing several times during successive periods of compressed measurements in order to apply Monte Carlo averaging to ensure accuracy. Because the SNR varies over time, the curves may not match those seen in simulations. As a result, the false alarm rate and detection probability are averages over several realizations.

In terms of performance, Figure 3(a) demonstrates that there is a significant performance gap across all network sizes, with the cooperative detection probability for L channels being lower than that of the $L - 1$ best channels. This finding demonstrates how choosing the most dependable channels can increase detection accuracy. Meanwhile, the cooperative false alarm rate is shown in Figure 3(b), where a small decline is observed for smaller network sizes (3 or 4 users). However, this rise stays within the IEEE 802.22 standard's permitted bounds, showing that the framework retains a high degree of dependability even in the face of slight variations in false alarms. The resilience of the cooperative detection framework under varied situations is thus demonstrated by this SDR-based implementation, which confirms the suggested method in a real-world setting.

Fig. 2. SDR-based Cooperative Compressed Sensing framework.

Fig. 3. Detection performance: (a) Q_d of L Vs L-1 channels. (b) Q_f of L Vs L-1 channels.

VII. CONCLUSION

In this study, we introduced a novel CCS method designed for cognitive radio networks that function in difficult environments like deep fading and high shadowing. Significant performance increases in CS were shown in early simulations driven by a sparse wideband signal, especially in challenging scenarios like the removal of a secondary user from the network. We used an SDR-based implementation to evaluate our methodology in an actual environment. With exact frequency, phase, and timing calibrations to guarantee synchronized, accurate cooperative detection, this useful framework used a HackRF One transmitter, eight USRP B210 receivers, and a centralized fusion center. The SDR-based validation strengthened our approach's potential for practical implementation by confirming its effectiveness and robustness. Key findings from simulation and SDR-based assessments were as follows:

- Robust Cooperative Compressed Sensing.
- Good performance in moderate SNR regimes.
- False Alarm Control.
- Flexibility and Adaptability.

Even though the current study uses both simulated and real-world SDR implementations to evaluate the suggested CSS strategy, there are still a number of areas that require more investigation and improvement:

- Extending the SDR implementation to handle real-time processing constraints.
- Developing adaptive algorithms that can respond to real-time changes.
- Enhanced Fusion Techniques.
- Energy Efficiency and Computational Optimization.

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